

Effects of Cubing and Jigsaw Strategies on Achievement in Geometry Concept among Secondary School Students in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of Cubing and Jigsaw Strategies on achievement in Geometry Concept among secondary school Students in Rivers State, Nigeria. Using a quasi-experimental design, 57 Senior Secondary 2 (SS2) students (29 males and 28 females) from three schools during the 2024/2025 academic session in the study. A validated Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) with reliability coefficient of 0.73, was used to measure students' achievement before and after a four-week intervention period. Results indicate that students taught using the Cubing strategy achieved the highest post-test mean scores, followed by those in the Jigsaw group, with the lecture-based method being the least effective. A significant difference was found between the two cooperative learning strategies and the conventional lecture method. However, gender did not significantly influence achievement scores, nor was there a significant interaction effect between gender and teaching strategy. These findings support the integration of cooperative learning strategies to enhance mathematics education, particularly in addressing the persistent challenges of poor student achievement in Nigerian schools. The study recommended increased adoption of student-centred and gender-neutral instructional strategies such as Cubing and Jigsaw, for increased achievement in mathematics.

Keywords: Cubing, Jigsaw, Cooperative Learning, Geometry, Achievement

Introduction

Mathematics is a fundamental subject essential for individual academic growth and the technological advancement of societies. It involves the exploration of patterns, structures, and relationships through logical reasoning and quantitative techniques (Yadaz, 2019). Mathematics covers areas such as numbers, operations, algebra, geometry, calculus, statistics, and probability (Fachgesellschaften & Socits, 2022). According to Yadaz (2019), Mathematics is a universal language and a vital tool for problem-solving across disciplines. Additionally, it provides a framework for understanding the world and making accurate predictions using models, formulas, and equations (Fachgesellschaften & Socits, 2022). Both theoretical and applied aspects of Mathematics are present in fields like physics, engineering, economics, computer science, and cryptography (Yadaz, 2019).

Geometry, a crucial branch of Mathematics in Nigeria's senior secondary education, is vital due to its practical applications in fields such as architecture, engineering, and design (Nneji, 2017). It strengthens spatial reasoning, enabling students to visualize and manipulate objects, which is key for problem-solving (Awofala & Lawani, 2020). Furthermore, geometry nurtures logical reasoning and deductive thinking which promotes a structured approach to mathematical proofs and problem-solving (Usman & Umoru, 2019). Visualization skills are central to geometry because students interpret visual information through diagrams, models, and notation which are valuable skills in the digital era (Olayemi, 2018). The importance of geometry is reflected in examinations like WAEC, where it covers shapes, theorems, angles, and practical applications. Okereke (2022) found that 41% of WASSCE Mathematics marks stem from geometry-related questions, underlining its significance for passing the subject.

Despite its importance, poor performance in geometry remains a challenge in Nigeria. WAEC reports from 2011 to 2020 show that students struggle with proofs, spatial reasoning, and visualization, often avoiding questions that are related to geometry (WAEC, 2011-2020). Fabiyi (2017) attributes these difficulties to insufficient foundational knowledge, poor teaching methods, and limited instructional resources. Additionally, research suggests that teacher-centered methods lead to shallow understanding, discouraging meaningful engagement with Mathematics concepts (Cherner et al., 2016; Yemi, Azid & Ali, 2018). Addressing these instructional weaknesses is critical to improving student outcomes in geometry.

Poor performance in Mathematics is a prevalent issue in developing countries, with students facing persistent challenges in the subject (Sa'ad, Adamu & Sadiq, 2014; Ojukwu, 2016; Olanrewaju & Suleiman, 2019). In Nigeria, Mathematics is often regarded as one of the most daunting subjects. The Chief Examiners' Annual Reports of WAEC (2019-2022) indicate that only a small percentage of students achieve credit passes in Mathematics in the Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE). The passing rates have steadily declined, from 33.19% in 2019 to 28.41% in 2022 (WAEC, 2019-2022). This emphasizes the urgent need for effective teaching strategies to improve students' performance and understanding of Mathematics.

Researchers have increasingly advocated for the use of learner-centered instructional approaches that promote collaboration, engagement, and the development of problem-solving skills (Achor, Imoko & Uloko, 2017). One such approach is the Jigsaw Cooperative Learning Strategy, which encourages cooperative learning by dividing students into small, interdependent groups, where each group is responsible for mastering a segment of a lesson and then sharing their knowledge with the class. This method fosters collaboration and critical thinking, as students actively engage with the material and rely on each other for deeper understanding (Timayi, Bolaji & Kajuru, 2015).

The Jigsaw Cooperative Learning Strategy is a student-centred instructional approach developed by Elliot Aronson in 1971 to foster cooperation and reduce racial tensions in desegregated classrooms. It encourages collaboration by dividing learning material among students, who become “experts” on their assigned sections and then teach their peers in their home groups. This method enhances engagement, comprehension, and peer interaction (Aronson, 1971, as cited in Jamilu, Iliyasu, Shehu & Vincent, 2022).

Over time, the strategy evolved to improve its effectiveness and adaptability. According to Hance (2016), Jigsaw I was the original model, where students worked in expert groups before returning to teach their peers, with individual assessments measuring learning outcomes. Jigsaw II, refined by Robert Slavin, introduced group rewards, ensuring that individual success contributed to overall group achievement, increasing motivation (Hance, 2016). Jigsaw III, developed by Glenn Stahl, incorporated periodic review sessions and assessments after expert discussions to reinforce learning. Finally, Jigsaw IV, introduced by Susan Holliday, added teacher interventions, allowing instructors to support struggling students, ensuring that all participants could engage effectively (Hance, 2016). Through these refinements, the Jigsaw strategy has become a widely used cooperative learning technique, promoting critical thinking, teamwork, and academic achievement across various subjects (Slavin, 2014).

Yemi, Azid, and Ali (2018) studied the Jigsaw Strategy in Mathematics among 80 SS1 students in Gombe State, using a quasi-experimental design. Their findings showed that students exposed to the Jigsaw strategy outperformed those taught conventionally. Similarly, Timayi, Bolaji, and Kajuru (2015) analyzed the Jigsaw IV Cooperative Learning Strategy (J4CLS) in Geometry among 144 students in Kaduna State, revealing significant improvements in the experimental group with no gender differences. On the other hand, the Cubing Cooperative Learning Strategy integrates cooperative learning principles with differentiated instruction, enhancing students' grasp of complex mathematical concepts (Achor et al., 2017). By assigning tasks aligned with Bloom's Taxonomy, such as describing, comparing, associating, analyzing, applying and arguing, students engage in a range of intellectually stimulating activities that cater to diverse learning styles. This promotes active participation, increases motivation, and improves knowledge retention (Achor et al., 2017).

The Cubing Instructional Strategy is a student-centred, constructivist approach that encourages learners to explore a concept from multiple perspectives through six cognitive tasks: describing, comparing, analyzing, applying, associating, and arguing (Gregory & Chapman, 2002). This strategy promotes critical thinking and problem-solving by guiding students through structured activities tailored to their readiness levels, interests, and learning profiles. Initially introduced by Gregory and Chapman (2002) as part of differentiated instructional strategies, Cubing was later reinforced by Bender (2008), who emphasized its effectiveness in enhancing learning outcomes, particularly for students with learning disabilities. The David Douglas School District (n.d.) further documented its instructional benefits, demonstrating that Cubing fosters active engagement and higher-order thinking. Over time, the strategy has evolved to incorporate technology, cooperative learning, and interdisciplinary applications, making it a valuable pedagogical tool in modern education (Literacy Leader, n.d.).

Okeke, Ramaila, and Ukoh (2023) compared contextualized cubing and conventional instruction in Physics among 107 students in Ibadan, finding that contextualized cubing significantly enhanced academic performance. Salha et al. (2017) examined the Cubing strategy among 100 seventh-grade female Mathematics students in Qalqilya Governorate, showing higher achievement and positive attitudes in the experimental group. These studies highlight the effectiveness of student-centred strategies like Jigsaw and Cubing in improving academic performance.

Regarding the interaction effect of gender and cooperative learning strategies, research suggests that cooperative learning can help reduce gender-related performance disparities. Studies have found no significant gender differences in achievement when cooperative learning approaches were used, indicating that these strategies create a more inclusive learning environment where all students can thrive academically, regardless of gender (Nwachukwu & Eke, 2023; Habtamu et al., 2022).

Given the educational challenges in Rivers State, exploring strategies like Cubing and Jigsaw is crucial to improving students' mathematics performance. This study therefore, aimed to investigate the effect of both the Jigsaw and Cubing Cooperative Learning Strategies on secondary school students' mathematics achievement in Rivers State. In addressing gaps in current literature, the research sought to provide evidence-based recommendations for mathematics educators and policymakers, encouraging the adoption of innovative strategies that foster deeper understanding, improve learning outcomes, and enhance students' overall performance in mathematics.

Students in Rivers State, Nigeria, struggle with geometry, contributing to poor mathematics performance (Adewale & Uchenna, 2022; Okeke & Ramaila, 2023). Traditional lecture-based methods fail to foster deep understanding and engagement (Eze & Nwafor, 2021). While Cubing and Jigsaw strategies enhance learning, their effects on geometry achievement in Nigerian schools remain underexplored. The Cubing strategy promotes higher-order thinking by analyzing concepts from multiple perspectives (Salha, Barakat, & Shawahany, 2017), while the Jigsaw strategy fosters collaboration through peer teaching (Josiah & Mankilik, 2021). However, most studies focus on physics and general mathematics, leaving a gap in their application to geometry, which demands strong spatial reasoning. This study examines the comparative effects of Cubing and Jigsaw strategies on geometry achievement among secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings will provide empirical insights into the most effective approach for enhancing geometry instruction and improving student performance.

Objectives of the Study

1. To investigate the effect of jigsaw and cubing strategies on achievement in Geometry concept among secondary school students in Rivers State.
2. To examine the interaction effect of gender and the strategies on achievement in Geometry concept among secondary school students in Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Geometry concept using Cubing and Jigsaw Strategies?
2. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Geometry concept using Cubing and Jigsaw Strategies?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Geometry concept using Cubing and Jigsaw strategies.
2. There is no significant interaction effect of gender and strategies on students' mean achievement scores in Geometry concept.

Methodology

The study employed the Quasi-experimental design. The design was selected since it was imperative that the students' class arrangement will not be interrupted. The study used the population of 5,901, senior secondary 2 (SS 2) students during the 2024/2025 academic session in Rivers State, Nigeria. However, because of the huge size of the population, the researcher chose a sample from three schools comprising of 57 SS 2 students 29 males and 28 females and their average age of 16 years. A number of 18 students (9 males and 9 females) was identified as Cubing Group, while, 19 students (10 males and 9 females) were considered as Jigsaw Group. The lecture group had 10 males and 9 females. The Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was developed and validated to measure students' achievement. Its reliability was established using Kuder-Richardson 20 (0.73). The instrument included 50 multiple-choice questions covering topics in geometry (circle theorems, sine and cosine rules, area and volumes of solid shapes).

The experiment lasted for 8 weeks for the three groups: Cubing, Jigsaw and Lecture. First week was pretest, followed by teaching the students using the Cubing, Jigsaw and lecture methods. This lasted for four weeks and was followed by the

posttest. In conducting the Cubing Group, the assigned teacher implemented the Cubing Cooperative Learning Strategy as outlined below:

Results

Research Question 1:

What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Geometry concept using Cubing and Jigsaw Strategies?

Table 1: Mean achievement scores of students taught Geometry concept using Jigsaw Cooperative Learning, Cubing Cooperative Learning, Computer-Assisted Instruction (CAI) and lecture methods.

Variables	N	Pre-Test Mean	SD of Pre-Test	Post-Test Mean	SD of Post-Test
Jigsaw	20	29.80	8.79	75.40	5.94
Cubing	18	31.33	8.30	79.67	6.56
Lecture	19	37.16	8.54	66.42	5.50

Source: Field data (2025)

From Table 1, the Jigsaw group had a pre-test mean score was 29.80 with a standard deviation of 8.79, and the post-test mean was 75.40 with a standard deviation of 5.94. For the Cubing group, the pre-test mean was 31.33 (SD = 8.30), and the post-test mean was 79.67 (SD = 6.56). For the Lecture group, the pre-test mean was 37.16 (SD = 8.54), and the post-test mean was 66.42 (SD = 5.50). The Cubing group shows the highest post-test mean, followed by the Jigsaw group, with the Lecture group having the lowest post-test mean scores. This suggests that students taught using the Cubing Cooperative Learning Strategy had the highest achievement scores compared to those taught with Jigsaw or Lecture methods.

Research Question 2:

What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Geometry concept using Cubing and Jigsaw Strategies?

Table 4: Interaction effect of gender and cooperative learning strategies on students' mean achievement scores in Geometry concept.

Strategy	Gender	N	Pre-Test Mean	SD of Pre-Test	Post-test Mean	SD of Post-Test	Mean gain
Jigsaw	Male	10	26.00	7.9861	74.60	7.0585	48.60
	Female	10	33.60	8.2084	76.20	4.8259	40.70
Cubing	Male	9	30.44	7.6012	79.11	7.4237	48.67
	Female	9	32.22	9.7696	80.22	6.8150	48.00

Source: Field data (2025)

The results in Table 4 show that both Cubing and Jigsaw strategies improved students' mathematics achievement, but Cubing was more effective across both genders. Before instruction, females outperformed males in the pre-test for both strategies. After instruction, Cubing led to higher post-test scores, with males scoring 79.11 and females 80.22, compared to Jigsaw (males: 74.60, females: 76.20). In terms of mean gain, males in Cubing had the highest improvement (48.67), followed by males in Jigsaw (48.60), females in Cubing (48.00), and females in Jigsaw (40.70). These results indicate that Cubing is the more effective strategy for improving mathematics achievement, benefiting both genders more than Jigsaw.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Geometry concept using Cubing and Jigsaw strategies.

Table 2: ANCOVA on the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using Jigsaw and Cubing Cooperative Learning and those taught mathematics using lecture method.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1623.618a	2	811.809	21.235	.000
Intercept	304127.357	1	304127.357	7955.350	.000
STRATEGY	1623.618	2	811.809	21.235	.000
Error	2064.382	54	38.229		
Total	307441.000	57			
Corrected Total	3688.000	56			

R Squared = .440 (Adjusted R Squared = .420)

Source: Field data (2025)

From Table 2, it can be seen that STRATEGY has a p-value (0.000) which suggests that the teaching strategies had significant effect on the mean achievement scores of students, hence, the hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant difference among the mean achievement scores of pupils taught mathematics using Jigsaw Cooperative Learning, Cubing Cooperative Learning and lecture method. The order of the significance of difference was determined using Scheffe PostHoc analysis and presented in Table 3.2b.

Table 3: Scheffe PostHoc on Significant Difference among the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using Jigsaw Cooperative Learning, Cubing Cooperative Learning and Lecture methods.

(I) STRATEGY	(J) STRATEGY	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
CUBING	JIGSAW	6.4167*	2.00881	.009
	LECTURE	13.2456*	2.03370	.000
JIGSAW	CUBING	-6.4167*	2.00881	.009
	LECTURE	6.8289*	1.98079	.005
LECTURE	CUBING	-13.2456*	2.03370	.000
	JIGSAW	-6.8289*	1.98079	.005

Source: Field data (2025)

Table 3 revealed that Cubing Cooperative Learning emerged as the most effective method, significantly outperforming the Lecture method with a mean difference of 13.2456 (p = 0.000). Jigsaw Cooperative Learning ranked second, outperforming the Lecture method with a mean difference of 6.8289 (p = 0.005). The Lecture method was the least effective, consistently underperforming compared to the other strategies. No significant differences were observed among the top two methods (Cubing and Jigsaw) This suggests comparable effectiveness in promoting mathematics achievement and establishes an order of effectiveness as Cubing, Jigsaw, and Lecture, with the first two strategies demonstrating significant advantages over lecture method.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant interaction effect of gender and strategies on students’ mean achievement scores in Geometry concept.

Table 5: Analysis of covariance of interaction effect of gender and instructional strategies on students’ mean achievement scores in Geometry concept.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	634.502a	4	158.626	4.307	.007
Intercept	10916.441	1	10916.441	296.419	.000
PRETEST	216.831	1	216.831	5.888	.021
GENDER	.342	1	.342	.009	.924
STRATEGIES	333.028	1	333.028	9.043	.005
GENDER * STRATEGIES	1.320	1	1.320	.036	.851
Error	1215.314	33	36.828		
Total	223013.000	38			
Corrected Total	1849.816	37			

R Squared = .343 (Adjusted R Squared = .263)

Source: Field data (2025)

The results show that gender has no significant effect on students’ achievement scores ($p = 0.924$), and there is also no significant interaction between gender and the cooperative learning strategies ($p = 0.851$). However, the cooperative learning strategy itself significantly impacts achievement scores ($p = 0.005$). The pretest score is also a significant predictor ($p = 0.021$). Overall, the null hypothesis, which posits no significant interaction effect of gender and strategy, is not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study align with previous research advocating for the effectiveness of cooperative learning strategies in mathematics education. Olawale and Adebayo (2021) found that the Cubing strategy significantly improved students’ engagement and achievement, particularly in problem-solving tasks. Similarly, Okafor and Amah (2021) demonstrated that Jigsaw promotes collaborative problem-solving and enhances academic performance. The present study corroborates these findings, as both Jigsaw and Cubing resulted in improved post-test scores compared to conventional teaching methods. However, unlike some previous studies that found no significant difference between Jigsaw and Cubing (Nwachukwu & Eke, 2023), this study identified Cubing as the more effective strategy. This suggests that while both methods improve learning outcomes, Cubing may provide a more structured and differentiated approach to mathematical problem-solving.

The study found no significant interaction between gender and cooperative learning strategies, reinforcing the view that both Jigsaw and Cubing provide equitable learning opportunities. This aligns with Okafor and Amah (2021), who reported that cooperative learning minimizes gender-based performance disparities. However, a minor trend in this study suggests that males slightly outperformed females in the mean gain scores within the Cubing group, while the Jigsaw group showed a more balanced improvement between genders. This suggests that while both strategies are effective for all learners, slight variations in cognitive engagement may exist based on individual learning styles rather than gender differences.

Given the persistent low mathematics achievement rates reported in Nigerian secondary schools, as highlighted in the WAEC reports (2019-2022), the adoption of Cubing and Jigsaw as instructional strategies could serve as a practical intervention to improve learning outcomes. These methods not only boost academic achievement but also promote engagement, motivation,

and retention of mathematical concepts. Furthermore, as both strategies prove effective across gender lines, they provide a sustainable framework for inclusive mathematics education.

However, challenges such as overcrowded classrooms, inadequate teacher training, and limited instructional resources (Olanrewaju & Yusuf, 2023; Habtamu, Mulugeta & Mulugeta, 2022; Olanrewaju & Yusuf, 2023; Zhang & Chen, 2023) must be addressed to ensure the successful implementation of cooperative learning in Rivers State. Providing professional development programs for teachers, improving classroom infrastructure, and incorporating technology-assisted cooperative learning could further enhance the effectiveness of Cubing and Jigsaw in mathematics instruction.

Conclusion

This study provides empirical evidence that Jigsaw and Cubing Cooperative Learning Strategies significantly improve students' mathematics achievement compared to traditional lecture methods. While both strategies enhance learning outcomes, Cubing demonstrated a slightly higher effectiveness. Gender had no significant impact on achievement, suggesting that these strategies provide inclusive and equitable learning opportunities for all students. The findings reinforce the importance of interactive and student-centred approaches in addressing Nigeria's mathematics education challenges.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following were recommended:

1. Educational institutions should prioritize the adoption of Cubing and Jigsaw strategies in mathematics instruction, as these methods have been proven to enhance students' achievement in Geometry more effectively than traditional lecture methods.
2. Teachers should implement gender-inclusive cooperative learning practices, ensuring that both male and female students actively participate and benefit equally from Cubing and Jigsaw strategies in mathematics classrooms.

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